

BOOK REVIEW

Re-Symbolization of the Self: Human Development and Tarot Hermeneutic, by Inna Semetsky, Rotterdam, Boston, Taipei, Sense Publications, 2011, 189pp.

Reviewed by Robert Mitchell

Jung biographer Laurens van der Post, in his introduction to Sally Nichols' *Jung and Tarot* (1980), expresses the theme of Dr. Inna Semetsky's book: "[Awareness includes] all sorts of non-rational forms of perception and knowing [that bridge the gap] between the inexhaustible wealth of, as yet, unrealized meaning in the collective unconscious, [and the conscious mind]" (p. xiv). The purpose of Dr. Semetsky's book is to build on this underlying assertion of C.G. Jung's *individuation* process—seeking wholeness by re-centering the personality in the Self, rather than the ego. Semetsky shows Tarot as a symbolic system to aid the individual on his/her individuation journey.

In her own words Semetsky says, "This book will demonstrate that Tarot ... plays a significant role in the process of self-formation or construction of human subjectivity, thus becoming a means for the re-symbolization of the Self" (p. 5). Semetsky goes beyond Nichols' illumination of the symbolism in the 22 cards of the Major Arcana to examine Tarot hermeneutic as a way of elevating into consciousness the affective awareness of our intuitive, instinctive and feeling-toned perceptions as they relate to real life experiences.

The goal of including Tarot readings in both therapy and psychological counseling is an important adjunct to Nichol's classic work. Yet Semetsky tells us, "There was no aim to prove or disprove anything, to qualify or disqualify, to compare or contrast. This study grew out of a desire to bring light to the often misunderstood realm of Tarot which is so much richer and valuable than its reductive popular role as a fortune-telling device" (p. 7).

As she says in her introduction to *Jung and Educational Theory* (2013), Semetsky has laid out her argument as a "theory-practice nexus that overcomes the Cartesian mind-body dualism" ("Introduction: Jung and *holistic* education," p. xii). She goes on to explain that Tarot hermeneutic serves post-formal, adult education, where the individuation process comes directly from life experiences. Thus, Tarot hermeneutic provides a different perspective from the Jungian concept of a clinically guided internal *active imagination* dialogue, and does not belong exclusively to the second half of life. Tarot hermeneutic embraces all adults in post-formal, self-education counseling.

Semetsky constructs her theoretical argument in four chapters.

She begins with the concept that mythic "reality" and objective "reality" are interwoven, and the integration of "esoteric" and "objective" worldviews creates wholeness in the individual personality and in the culture. Tarot is a symbolic system that helps bring to consciousness an inherent memory of mythic reality that speaks to our affective faculties.

JPSE II (2014)

She says, “true intelligence cannot be reduced to a rational understanding alone; it is our human experience that can bring a soul to life and enrich education with its spiritual dimension” (p. 29). This interdependence results in a “relational” worldview, and “a relational approach most strongly manifests in the ethics of care” (p. 30), a term Semetsky borrows from education philosopher Nel Noddings to describe an *erotic*, or relational, engagement with the world.

This erotic engagement takes place at the archetypal level. In a Tarot reading, the seeker, whose role in the reading is that of the “hero” represented by the card labeled the Fool, “becomes capable of overcoming obstacles, defeating adversaries or ... winning over his own complexes, anxieties and fears” (p. 33) along the symbolic journey laid-out in the 22 cards of the Major Arcana. The images, Semetsky tells us, quoting Jung, “were distantly descended from the archetypes of transformation” (p. 34). Therefore, “[t]he journey through Tarot images is practically a dynamic search for identity and the discovery of meaning and value in our lives via creative encounters with the unconscious in the process of individuation.” (p. 34).

Having initially based her premise on Jungian psychological concepts, Semetsky expands this base, drawing on theories of personality development and consciousness from other philosophers and psychologists, quoting liberally from Nel Noddings, Abraham Maslow, Carl Rogers, Martin Buber and others. Here, she diverges from the Jungian concept of an inwardly focused ego-archetype axis accessed through active imagination to address the individual “as enmeshed in the network of relationships” (p. 52). A psychotherapeutic understanding of this network of relationships can employ many non-verbal modalities, which include pictorial communication. She says, “Tarot hermeneutic ... can create a symbolic bridge to the archetypal depth of the internal world of ‘the other’” (p. 52). In this way, we can engage the other not only on an interpersonal but on an intra-psychical level to address our own psychological conflicts arising from insecurity, anger, depression, frustration, anxiety, confusion, exhaustion, feeling overwhelmed and/or indecisive, etc. She continues, “The list is endless, and our real-life experience always presents new contexts and encounters that call for new evaluations, new meanings, and more education in practice” (p. 59).

To illuminate this relationship between therapy and education of the Self, Semetsky draws on the philosophy of Gilles Deleuze. She says, “Jung’s dynamic process of the individuation of the Self as the goal of analysis is akin to Deleuze’s concept of *becoming*, and specifically *becoming-other* as a process of learning from the unconscious embedded in experience ... the world consists not of substantial ‘things’ but of relational entities, or multiplicities” (p. 61). Subjectivity, then, is embedded in the relational dynamics of experiment and experience.

This concept at the heart of Semetsky’s argument takes the individual’s relationship to the spirit realm of the collective unconscious outside of the inwardly focused ego-archetype axis and places it in the context of an erotic, or relational, engagement with the world. “It is not the possibilities of our conscious mind but the multiple ‘things in the psyche’ as parameters of the unconscious that continuously create novel relations in our

JPSE II (2014)

real experience ... capable of *affecting* and *effecting* changes, thus contesting the very identity of subjects on the road to individuation” (p. 64). Semetsky tells us that the ego-archetype relationship is enfolded in a free-flowing cloud, like an invisible fog that penetrates and enfolds the psyche: quoting Deleuze, Semetsky says “We ‘are never separate from the World; the interior is a selected exterior, and the exterior is a projected interior’” (p. 75). In this way, we are all enfolded in an integrated mythic/objective reality accessible as both affective and rational awareness. Tarot hermeneutic can help us interpret our affective awareness and re-center the personality in the Self so that our lives express this more complete, integrated “reality.”

The Nexus that connects theory and practice is the Tarot reading itself, of which Semetsky discusses two important factors. First is the relationship between the reader and the client in therapeutic, counseling and educational practice. This relationship, she says, depends on the reader becoming a “master of metaphors,” which Semetsky describes, using a term coined by anthropologist Claude Levi-Strauss, as becoming a *bricoleur*. Bricolage, she tells us, refers to the construction of an objective study that draws on phenomenology, hermeneutics and narratology, while retaining the rigor of critical thought and “paying particular attention to the webs of relationships, processes and interconnections among phenomena within which [the individual] is situated” (p. 11). Since the Tarot layout amplifies the unconscious content of archetypal images, “An expert reader as a genuine bricoleur can translate the pictorial language of symbols and signs into spoken word, thus creating a wealth of sympathetic, emotional data embodied in the unfolding narrative” (p. 16).

Interpretation by the reader is via the *a-causal* principle of synchronicity. “Implementing a phenomenological approach means to accurately describe a ‘given phenomenon as it presents itself in one’s own experience—not [to explain] its genesis through reference to antecedent causal factors.’” (p. 18). At the core of this relationship is the archetypal Eros, or relational, spirit-of-attraction that holds two opposites together, eventually reconciling “what analytical thinking habitually perceives dualistically” (p. 19). Thus, the Tarot reading functions *educationally* by focusing on the ethical and spiritual dimension of learning by experience and *existentially* on the construction of identity—the re-symbolization of the Self (p. 18).

Second, this Nexus takes place not in the objective world, but in the liminal space of the *Imaginal* world (p. 21). Access to this world is perceived through images, rather than thoughts, and explained in terms of the Projective Hypothesis that also lies at the foundation of the Rorschach test, sand play therapy, the I Ching and, perhaps, dream analysis. Semetsky explains that, by definition, “the projective hypothesis holds that an individual supplies structure to unstructured stimuli in a manner consistent with the individual’s own unique pattern of conscious and unconscious needs, fears, desires, impulses, conflicts, and ways of perceiving and responding” (p. 73). Thus, it organizes a person’s unique experience as “inseparable from her life-world” (p. 73). The archetypal forces affecting the personality and its relationships to the world are projected into the images that manifest in the spread. In the client’s shuffling of the cards, and the reader’s layout, Tarot hermeneutic is inseparable from the projective hypothesis.

JPSE II (2014)

To illustrate the practice of Tarot Reading, Dr. Semetsky uses a ten-card, Celtic Cross spread, laid out on the table before the client. Her fifteen sample readings are composed of four men and eleven women, primarily professional, white, black and Latino, ranging in age from their twenties to the plus forties. The spread tells a life-story with a focus on a specific question to be explored. Following the concepts of the Projective Hypothesis, Synchronicity and Bricolage, the spread is a product of “imagination.” Semetsky tells us that “Imagination pushes the Ego from its position in the center of the personality where it can comfortably focus on ‘self-regard [and] into a space where it can come face to face with others’” (p. 85).

The questions asked by her clients fall into three categories: professional/career issues; personal relationships; and individual insight. The first of these is most provocative, as it follows James Hillman’s argument that one’s “true” vocation stems from one’s archetypal essence. Yet a “true” vocation can be easily misdirected by social, peer, familial, religious and other pressures. What Dr. Semetsky presents, here, are not case studies, but individual readings. Generally, her clients report a positive experience. There is no follow up on how, or if, the problem presented was eventually resolved. I thought Semetsky’s narrative of the reading and interpretation of the spread could have benefitted from a more poetic touch, but not every reader will see it that way.

While she has been careful to document the restrictive clinical conditions under which the study was conducted, it could also have benefitted from a wider range of subjects— young people who have “dropped out,” entered a liminal space and want to become more conscious of the archetypal forces they have attracted to themselves; college students seeking to become aware of their true “vocations”; veterans whose combat trauma has made them ready for a life-transformation. What these practical examples do reveal is the sensitivity, intuition and connectedness of the reader to the client and how the imaginal modality and Tarot hermeneutic are beneficial in pushing the Ego aside so that the client, through a relationship with the reader, can “see” the archetypal forces at work in his/her life, and work at the project of re-symbolization of the Self—what Jungian psychologist Murray Stein calls the “individuation imperative.”

In her final chapters, Dr Semetsky returns to the original purpose of individuation, arguing that individuation takes place on the subjective level of both the individual and the cultural as a whole. Her final chapter takes aim at her critics and mounts an erudite defense of the role of Tarot hermeneutic in human development.

Dr Semetsky’s book opens our eyes to both a time-honored, traditional way of looking at an integrated “reality” and an important way of interpreting that reality as it presents itself in the daily lives of ordinary human beings.

References

- van der Post, L. (1980). Introduction to Nichols, S. *Jung and tarot: An archetypal journey*. New York: Samuel Weiser.
- Semetsky, I. (Ed.). (2013). *Jung and educational theory*. Oxford: Wiley-Blackwell.
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